

Performance Enhancement of DC Microgrid Using Energy Storage Systems under Dynamic Load Conditions

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Abstract: This paper investigates the coordinated control and optimization of DC shipboard power systems integrated with renewable energy sources and energy storage devices. Initially, a conventional DC system without storage was simulated, where sudden generator faults and load variations led to instability and partial power supply. To overcome these limitations, an Energy Storage System (ESS) was introduced through a bi-directional DC–DC converter, which ensured a continuous supply by injecting or absorbing power during faults and load fluctuations. The simulation results demonstrate that the ESS significantly reduces voltage ripples, maintains the DC bus reference voltage at 750 V, and improves overall reliability. Further, the system was extended to incorporate solar photovoltaic arrays and wind energy systems. The combined renewable-based DC microgrid maintained stable voltage levels and efficiently shared power among multiple loads under varying operating conditions. The coordinated control strategy successfully optimized power flow, minimized losses, and enhanced fault tolerance. The outcomes validate the effectiveness of integrating ESS and renewable sources for achieving a resilient, reliable, and sustainable DC shipboard power system.

Keywords: DC Microgrid, Energy Storage System, Renewable Sources, Coordinated Control PV Array, PWM Generator, PMSG, Battery, wind, MATLAB 2016.

I. Introduction

To meet the growing energy demand, reduce CO₂ emissions, and cope with environmental concerns, renewable energy is expected to play a key role in the future. This clean offshore energy can be integrated at the transmission level as well as at the distribution level. At the transmission level, wind energy is the main driver, particularly in Europe. For example in northern Europe, one can witness many wind farms connected to the main transmission grid via AC or DC links. Due to their intermittent nature and the fact that these wind farms are connected to the grid via power electronics converters, the power grid becomes more vulnerable and subject to instability. With more power electronics converters in the power grid, the power network will have reduced inertia and consequently will be more prone to frequency and angle instability as transient stability phenomena. Though these issues are not within the scope of the thesis, they are a driver for addressing renewable energy sources (renewables) in a more efficient way, avoiding to bring instability for the main grid. In the medium and low voltage distribution level, until recently, substations were load axis connected and always represented positive loads, implying in a static sizing and implementation of this distribution grid. From now on, these distribution substations will often represent negative loads, mainly due to the integration

of Photo-Voltaic (PV) energy as shown in the following figure. The integration of Distributed Generation (DG) in the grid changes the behavior of consumers who may also become producers. Figure (1.1) [3] shows the load profile for a substation in countryside Germany where it can be seen that much solar power was included to the grid. While during the night the load is roughly the same, during the day (when sun shines) the load becomes negative (power flux inversion flowing to the high voltage), and may represent several times the consuming load. Two power management philosophies can be used in order to deal with this new phenomena. The first way is to send this excess of power along the distribution network in order to be used where needed. This way of managing local production will generate constraints as power congestion, voltage instability and additional losses, what would need in many cases to re-size the distribution network, what is not a cost-effective way of managing the integration of this DG. The other way for managing DG is to either consume in nearby, or store the excess of power in order to be consumed later. This can be done via the so-called Micro Grid. In the future, in order to preserve network reliability and integrity, the electrical distribution system operator will impose additional constraints (Grid Codes) on decentralized renewable energy producers.

DC Micro Grid: For large scale development and integration of renewables, it is necessary to solve the intermittency problem of DG. To attain this goal, we consider a storage system to increase the penetration of this type of energy. But a power flow management in this new type of system then becomes necessary, bringing us to the concept of Microgrids. Microgrids appear as a solution to integrate renewable energy sources, to meet the requirements of network operators, and ensure the reactivity of the electrical system to unpredictable energy sources. Two different types of Microgrids can be considered: AC Micro Grids are not the focus of this thesis we will indeed focus on DC Microgrids in the following. Since PVs' output is in the form of Direct Current, as well as several storage systems as batteries and supercapacitors, DC grids can be used as an efficient system for integrating renewables, for assuring energy security and protecting power systems. For this reason, it seems natural in this work to consider a DC grid to integrate sources as PV arrays and storage. The produced energy is then integrated to an AC grid through a power converter. In the same way, several loads (in particular electric vehicles) are naturally DC, and the use of a DC Micro Grid allows to reduce power losses and to guarantee a better power quality. The DC Micro Grid developed in this study is able to correctly feed a load of desired power while ensuring voltage stability, to assure reliability against strong changes in the grid like faults, and to eliminate disturbances and to assure high power quality.

The DC Microgrid guarantees the power exchange with the main grid and can also supply loads such as charging stations for electric cars. The objective of this study is the stabilisation of the DC Micro Grid's voltage in spite of variations on production and consumption, to create a reliable and independent system. For that we will exploit the physical characteristics of each element of system. In the framework of this thesis, we have a decentralized source interconnected through a power converter to a DC Micro Grid and a storage system composed by a battery for long energy needs and a supercapacitor for rapid variations of production or the load. Because of the objective of assuring stable and performing operation in a wide range of situations, and because the nature of the considered systems is nonlinear, it was mainly used nonlinear control theory to develop the algorithms. In the same way, an important characteristic of the Micro Grid studied is its ability to disconnect from the main grid and to operate in island mode.

II. Block Diagram of Dc Shipboard Power System

In this DC SPS for power generation, diesel generators are used. It follows the HVDC working principle where

the generated ac is converted into dc through converters (i.e., Rectifiers) and from DC bus again reconverted into AC near loads. The battery is used as a backup. The basic block is shown in fig.1

Figure.1 Block diagram of DC shipboard power system

Generally, there are three processes in this DC shipboard power system. The three processes are power generation, power conversion, power distribution, and the load.

III. Power generation

This module deals with the generation of power. The power generated in this module is distributed to the loads. Generally, in marine industry for power generation diesel generators are used. Primarily gas turbines are used in marine vessels. But for now diesel generators are implemented. A diesel engine and alternator combined called as diesel generator. Diesel engines drive generator to generate electricity. Diesel engine is a ignition engine uses diesel as fuel. The primary working of diesel generator is to transforms mechanical energy into electrical energy by using diesel as fuel. Generally diesel generator embraces of three parts they are diesel engine, AC synchronous generator, and control panel. The working of diesel generator set is that in diesel engine the air is pulled into the cylinder and the compressed which increases the temperature. The compressed air is heated at high temperature at 700 – 900°C and high pressure. The diesel is the expanded

in to the cylinder which combust. This forces the piston to work and thus the heat energy is converted into mechanical energy. Hence the diesel engine transforms heat energy to mechanical energy. Now the diesel generator transforms mechanical energy to electrical energy. An alternator is paired with the diesel engine. This alternator transforms the mechanical energy into electrical energy. In total the diesel engine operation is completed in four steps that is intake, compression, expansion and exhaust.

Now a day the renewable energy systems have been gaining popularity. These renewable energy system can replace the diesel generator by solar and wind plants.

Working of DC Shipboard: The working of this DC SPS starts with the diesel generator. These diesel generators take the fuel as input produce electricity in the form of alternating current (AC). This Alternating Current (AC) is transported to converter. Where converter acts as rectifier and transforms Alternating Current (AC) into Direct Current (DC). This converted DC is given to the busbar. Bus bar transfers the power from input to the end consumers. At the load side again this DC is given to load side converter which acts as inverter and transforms DC into AC.

The converted AC is given to the loads as per requirements. Whenever there is fault in the system the protecting devices operates and makes it isolated if the ESS device is not used. It takes time to lucid the fault which means there will interruption in power supply to the loads. By using ESS system whenever there is a fault in the system then these ESS provides required supply to the system to pre-eminent reliability.

If there is any fault in the generation the circuit breaker triggers and isolated with the un faulted system. Then the power required by the respective load is regale by ESS i.e., battery integrated with DC/DC converter. When there is need of power from ESS system the battery voltage is stepped up by using DC/DC converter. This DC/DC converter is combination of buck boost converter. When there is need of stepping up the voltage the battery voltage is boosted up using boost converter and injects the voltage.

Whenever there is any fault near load the circuit breaker stumble and isolates the faulted part from un faulted part. So the generated power gets wasted so in order to mitigate the waste and utilize it the ESS system is beneficial. The extra generated power is used by ESS system to charge the battery. Whenever there is extra generated power the DC/DC converter works as buck converter and observes the voltage.

IV. Simulation Model and Results

The proposed method is implemented and modeled in

MATLAB version.

Figure. 2 Simulation of DC Power System without ESS

In place of diesel generator to make circuit simple direct three phase source is used which produce rated voltage of 25kv 10MVA power with 50 Hz frequency. To reduce voltage to rated three phase voltage i.e., 415 a step-down transformer is used to decrease voltage. Three phase measurement device is used to gauge the voltage and current of generator and transformer. To avoid any harmonics or ripples present in voltage and current filters are used. Two filters are used in the circuit i.e., RL and RC filters are used to remove harmonics and RC is used to support voltage. The RL filter embrace of series concatenated resistance and inductance.

Figure. 3 Waveform of Generation Power

Two disturbances are created which occur commonly in system to validate the feasibility of the proposed approach. Two disturbances are generator loss, load start. The three generators output power waveforms are shown in figure 4. Whenever there fault in generation the protecting device that is circuit breaker isolates the faulted part with non faulted path. At generator 3 the

there is fault at generation at 4sec it becomes isolated and doesn't generate power. In matlabsimulink to produce fault the circuit breaker is set to trip at four seconds.

Figure.4 Waveform of Output Load Power

Power

The load power waveform is shown in figure 5. At four seconds the power is not generated due to generation fault i.e., power doesn't gets regale to the load. But in this concept all the bus bars are tied to together and a reference value is set at 750V. So whenever there is any fault occurred in generation the loads get partially regale. Because of the tied bus bar the power is distributed equally. In figure 5. it can be seen that the load is disconnected at 2-3 seconds so during that period the excess generated power is wasted. And because of the loss of one generated and distribution of power equally the loads may experience some large ripples and partially power is received by load that is load is not fully regale. Because the load needs 10kw of power but it regale with less than 10kw after fault occurrence. So in order to make power ripple free and to utilize the extra generated power and to supply the load with full supply even when fault has occurred Energy Storage System (ESS) is used.

DC Power System with ESS Device: The proposed method is implemented and modeled in MATLAB version 2016a with Intel quad core 7th generation as shown in Figure 6. Two-level pulse width-modulated (PWM), voltage source converters (VSCs) are used to convert the AC (3-φ 440 VAC 50Hz) power produced by the three-phase generators which is again stepped down using transformers. The DC bus reference voltage

is set to 750 V.

Figure 5 Simulation of DC Power System with ESS

As the feedback path Energy Storage System is used. A battery of 650V 400Ah is used in ESS and concatenated to the DC bus through a bi-directional DC/DC converter. In MATLAB for DC/DC converter a half-bridge converter is used. Pulse width modulation has been regale to it.

Figure 6 Waveform of Generation Power

Two disturbances are created which occur commonly in system to validate the feasibility of the proposed approach. Two disturbances are generator loss, load start. The three generators output power and battery power waveforms are shown in figure 7. And battery power is also shown in the waveform. If the battery power in the waveform is at zero w., then the battery is neither charging nor discharging. Whenever it is at +1 or greater, then it is charging and if it is on -1 or lesser, then it is discharging.

4.2 DC Shipboard Power System using multiple renewable energy sources

Fig. 7 DC micro grid system with multiple renewable sources

Fig. 8 Load power consumption changed at 2sec and 3sec

V. Conclusion

The simulation results clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of integrating Energy Storage Systems (ESS) and renewable sources into DC shipboard power systems. The conventional DC system without ESS suffered from instability, higher voltage ripples, and partial supply failures during sudden load variations or generator faults. With the inclusion of ESS through a bi-directional DC–DC converter, the DC bus voltage was maintained at the reference level of 750 V, ripple content was minimized, and uninterrupted power delivery was ensured.

References:

- [1] R. G. Blakey, "Power electronics in warships," *Power Engineering Journal*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 65-70, 1993.
- [2] Webstar, "Naval experience of power electronics maintenance," *IEE Colloquium on Power Electronics Reliability*, no. 202, 1998.
- [3] Z. Jin, G. Sulligoi, R. Cuzner, L. Meng, J. C. Vasquez, and J. M. Guerrero, "Next-generation shipboard DC power system: introduction smart grid and dc microgrid technologies into maritime electrical networks," *IEEE Electr. Mag.*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 45–57, 2016.
- [4] Vijay, R., "Quorum sensing driven bacterial swarm optimization to solve bacterial swarm optimization to solve practical dynamic power ecological emission economic dispatch", *International Journal of Computational Methods*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1850089-24, 2018.
- [5] Vijay R., "Optimal and reliable operation of microgrid using enriched Biogeography Based Optimization algorithm", *Journal of Electrical Engineering*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1-11, 2018.
- [6] Vijay, R. & Pavithra T., "Cost optimization of energy storage systems based on wind resources using gravitational search algorithm", *International Journal of Advanced Research*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 41667-1680, 2017.
- [7] Vijay, R., "Transmission Line Outage Detection and Identification by Communal Spider Optimization Algorithm", *CVR Journal of Science and Technology*, Vol.14, pp.38-42, 2018
- [8] G. Seenu Mani, J. Sun, and H. Peng, "Real-time power management of integrated power systems in all electric ships leveraging multi time scale property," *IEEE Transactions on Control Systems Technology*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 232–240, 2012.
- [9] S. Kim, S. Choe, S. Ko, and S. Sul, "A naval integrated power system with a battery energy

storage system: Fuel efficiency, reliability, and quality of power, *Electrification Magazine*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 22–33, 2015.

- [10] F. Shariat Zadeh, N. Kumar, and A. K. Srivastava, “Optimal control algorithms for reconfiguration of shipboard microgrid distribution system using intelligent techniques,” *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 474–482, 2017.
- [11] Skjong, E. Rodskar, M. Molinas, T. Johansen, and J. Cunningham, “The marine vessel’ electrical power system: From its birth to present day,” *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 103, pp. 2410–2424, 2015
- [12] J. F. Hansen, J. O. Lindtjorn, U.U. Odegaard, T.A. Myklebust, “Increased operational performance of OSVs by Onboard DC Grid,” 4th International Conference on Technology and Operation of Offshore Support Vessels, Singapore, 2011.
- [13] ABB, “Onboard DC Grid. The step forward in Power Generation and Propulsion,” Tech. rep., 2015.
- [14] W. Koczara and G. Iwanski, “Power Electronics for Renewable and Distributed Energy Systems Variable-Speed Power Generation,” Springer, 2013.
- [15] K. Hutton, B. Babaiahgari, and J.-D. Park, “A comparative study on electrical distribution systems for the US coast guard’s 270-ft medium endurance cutter,” *North American Power Symposium (NAPS)*, IEEE, pp. 1–6, 2016.